

Marketability of Filipino Teacher Education Graduates

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the marketability of the Teacher Education graduates of Cebu Normal University. Marketability yields specific skills required not only to gain employment but also attain one's capabilities in the dynamic workplaces. The study surveyed the Graduates of BEEd and BSEd degree programs across personal and professional qualities, special skills and training. It also viewed on marketability values and features on the graduate's employment data or experience adopted from the GTS questionnaires. The study utilized a combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis techniques. The results affirm that Cebu Normal University; Philippines Education graduates has competed the society that meet the needs of the employer. These pointed out the conclusion that the teacher education graduates are qualified to teach based on their own field of specialization. The study revealed that the graduates are employable based on the specialization. Furthermore, the study concluded that the teachers are qualified and possessed special skills as teachers in the 21st century.

Keywords: Marketability; Filipino teacher education graduates; Employability

1. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic institutions and organizations of the 21st century require skillful and proficient teachers who can think critically, make wise decision, creative, innovative and communicate well in a variety of contexts. UNESCO (2012) reported that modern economy needs highly trained and skilled human resource, and higher education institutions (HEIs) are required to produce qualified graduates to meet the needs of national development and employers.

It is common knowledge that employers prefer graduates that can get jobs done with the best outcome immediately upon hiring. As the number of graduates entering the job market increases, graduates now need to compete more than ever to get the best or the most suitable job. In the

increasingly competitive job market today, universities are constantly challenged to work harder to produce the most employable graduates to suit the needs and demands of today's dynamic workplaces. Many universities worldwide have identified "graduate employability" as one of its key performance indicator to vie for the best students and to remain as the institutions of choice for higher education. Indisputably, graduate employability is therefore, of strategic significance to nation building. Various graduate training schemes launched by the government to alleviate the numbers of jobless graduates. The real test for an educator or teacher and the greatness of universities lies in the employability of its graduates. Employability or 'to have employability skills' means specific skills are required not only to gain employment, but also to progress within an enterprise so as to achieve one's potential and contribute successfully to the enterprise's strategic directions (DEST, 2002).

As a teacher training institution, the primary goal of the Cebu Normal University, College of Teacher Education Programs is to produce good teachers who are qualified to teach in the elementary and secondary schools. Graduates in teacher education program are expected to have acquired teaching and competency skills during their pre-service training to be better prepared for the teaching profession. These skills include: lesson planning, preparation of instructional materials, use of a variety of methods, good communication skills, skills in the use of information technology, problem-solving skills, critical thinking skills, human relations skills and research skills.

For the individual, employability depends on the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values infatuated, the way these assets are used and presented to employers in a milieu. For example, personal circumstances and labor market environment within which the College of Teacher education graduates seek work. The idea for this dimension focuses on graduate employability issues, or rather, the lack of employability in the current local job market. Therefore, there is a need to make a transcribe study of the education graduates not only to trace them but more importantly to discover on how passable is the training provided by the College of Teacher Education in the overall performance of their profession, the employment status of the graduates as well as their achievements in the field.

Education in the 21st century highlights globalization. This implies that patterns of goods and services rendered in the workplace be determined by how much and to what extent do the knowledge, skills and attitudes as well as technology-based competitive advantages required by the global standards are performed effectively and efficiently.

Becker (1993) defines marketability as the individual's ability to obtain and retain a job. In addition, a marketable person is someone who is motivated, self-confident, committed, adaptable, and flexible. He or she is also a team player, and articulate communicator. Brown and Layder, 1996; Lall 2000; Lewin 1998 posit that when markets are shifting from the local to global arena, countries that want to survive the global competition of the future are facing tremendous pressures to improve the quality of their work.

The definition used by Peter Husz is as follows: "By human capital we mean the time, experience, knowledge and abilities of an individual household or a generation, which can be used in the production process" (1998). Others only define human capital investment, e.g. Schultz (1992) defines human capital investments as enrolment rates multiplied by the cost of education for one individual. Lucas (1988) measures human capital probably by expenditures on education and "external" human capital, which he believes to be able to measure by calculating the returns to land.

The theory on human capital by Becker suggests that an individual be compensated for the work he or she performs, as well as for the use of that individual's human capital. According to Elman and O'rand (2004) human capital theory and its variants are among the most common explanations of the school-wage relationship. Human capital acquisition is viewed as a lifelong process, although the theory differentiates the components of human capital attainment into those that fall before and those that follow employment. In the same study, they added that educational attainment reflects expected wage remuneration and predicts labor market placement

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The study investigated the determinants towards employability of the Cebu Normal University, Education Graduates for Academic Year 2012, 2013 and 2014. It looked into the graduates' characteristics, employability values and significant attributes of the graduates.

2. SHORT LITERATURE REVIEW

In a study done in University Utara Malaysia, significant predictors for unemployed graduates are ethnicity, English language proficiency, and types of degree obtained. In that study, statistical profiling of unemployed graduates is dominated by Malays, females and with respect to degrees, BBA (Bachelor of Business Administration) form the largest group of unemployed graduates (Lim, 2008).

From the employer's perspective, today's graduates are lacking personality management skills (i.e. positive attitudes, responsibility, adaptability, leadership), exploration skills (i.e. not being imaginative, innovative, critical & creative thinking) and connectivity skills (i.e. communication, IT, team-working, commercial awareness). Hence, academic achievement alone is insufficient for graduates to gain employment (Mohamad and Hamzah, 2009). Furthermore, graduates have a poor command of English, poor character, attitude or personality and asking for unrealistic salary/benefits are a few of the problems faced by employers when hiring fresh graduates.

These findings are important in planning programs to improve the College of Teacher Education Program at the same time give direction on what more can be done to train our education students to meet the demands of teaching. Hillage and Pollard's (1998) widely- cited definition of employability as an individual's ability to gain initial employment, maintain employment, move between roles within the same organization, obtain new employment if required and ideally secure suitable and sufficiently fulfilling work. Mantz Yorke added that "employability refers to a graduate's achievements and his/her potential to obtain a "graduate job", and should not be confused with the actual acquisition of a "graduate job" (which is subject to influences in the environment, a major influence being the state of the economy. There is some evidence suggest that references to employability make the implicit assumption that graduates are young people. The risk is not considering employability in respect of older graduates who have the potential to bring a more extensive life. Employability is not merely an attribute of the new graduate. It needs to be continuously refreshed throughout a person's working life.

The University of Sydney believes that graduates should be more employable, more able to cope with change and more developed as people. The much more recent Dearing Report (NCIHE, 1997) drew particular attention to the vital role that higher education plays in a modern economy. Global competitiveness required that education and training should enable people in an advanced society to compete with the best in the world (NCIHE 1997).

The marketability of a person is also determined by his or her ability to actively involved in co-curriculum activities in school, knowledge in IT, proficient in English, confident and have

planning for the future upon graduation from university (Kabul, et al 2009). It is indicated that leadership skills, communication skills and conflict management skills are some of the employability skills desired by employers (Robinson, 2006). In Woods and King (2002), they stressed that communication skills include oral communication skills, written communication skills, listening skills, face-to-face communication skills and the ability to resolve conflicts positively.

The employability of graduates has become an aim that governments around the world have, to varying extents, imposed on national higher education systems. This interest in employability reflects an acceptance of human capital theory (Becker 1975), under human capital theory, the task of government is to foster conditions that encourage growth in the stock of human capital, since this is seen as vital to performance of knowledge-based economies in a globalized society (Kabul, et al, 2009).

Education and training providers have a statutory duty to evaluate their own activities and participate in external evaluations. Evaluation is used to collect data in support of education policy decisions and as a background for information- and performance-based steering.

Employability has been used as a performance indicator for higher education institutions (Smith et al, 2000) and represents a form of work specific (pro) active adaptability that consists of three dimensions: career identity, personal adaptability and social and human capital (Fugate et al, 2004).

According to Hills, Robertson, Walker, Adey, and Nixon (2003) in de Guzman and Castro (2008) the role of the higher education sector is to supply suitably skilled graduates to the workplace (p. 211). However, de la Harpe, Radloff, and Wyber, in a study conducted in 2000, suggest that there is worldwide concern that existing undergraduate programs are not producing graduates of lifelong learning with the professional skills they need in order to succeed. The issue of employability, as Homes (2001) says, "will be a key quality issue for many years to come".

UNESCO (1980), in a study, observed that in job recruitment, employers' priority may determine the importance of various skills and attitudes for certain job categories. Despite a number of similarities among employers it was observed that either for "promotion" or "hiring" certain criteria have higher ranking in the order of importance, for example, age, sex, religion or beliefs. However, education is very important as recruitment criteria. For educational management positions, professional experience and educational qualifications rank highest. One striking result in the UNESCO (1980) study was the importance of age, when employers are recruiting supervisors and secretaries. But age comes first when recruiting unskilled operators. Employers prefer recruiting managers and supervisors from within the firm because such position often requires job experience (UNESCO, 1980).

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study used a combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis techniques. The qualitative research approaches seek to understand a given research problem or topic from the perspectives of the local population it involves (Cohen et al., 2009). According to Fellows and Liu (2006) a qualitative research, an exploration of the subject is undertaken without prior formulations in the object to gain understanding and collect information and data such that theories will emerge. In quantitative design approach, it is focused on the collection and analysis

BEED Gen Ed	142	135	95.1%	101	86	85.15%	118	115	97.45 %
BEED ECE	94	90	95.7%	58	50	86.2%	56	54	96.4%
BEED SPED	87	82	94.3%	62	55	88.7%	83	82	98.8%
BSED Math	78	76	97.4%	56	51	91.1%	69	64	92.7%
BSED English	86	82	95.3%	70	62	88.6%	87	85	97.7%
BSED Filipino	24	22	91.7%	14	13	92.9%	32	31	96.8%
BSED Soc. Studies	12	11	91.7%	9	7	77.8%	19	17	89.47 %
BSED Physical Science	16	16	100%	12	11	91.7%	12	11	91.6%
BSED Biological Science	20	19	95%	18	16	88.9%	25	22	88%
BSED MAPEH	20	15	75%	25	20	80%	27	24	88.88 %
BSED TLE	5	5	100%	5	5	100%	10	8	8%
TOTAL	584	553	94.7%	430	376	87.4%	538	513	95.35 %

To gather in-depth information on employability of the CNU-CTE graduates, e-groups was retrieved and the researchers communicated the respondents personally and via facebook (Boholano, 2012). In the teaching arena, the percentage of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) who graduated last March 2012 have greater job opportunity compared to those who graduated a year after. All BSED Physical Science and TLE graduates are marketable of the 2012. This shows that goods and services they have rendered in the workplace are firm by how much and to what extent do their knowledge, skills, attitudes and values required by the overall standards, since most number of batch 2012 graduates are in the workstation.

The time, practice, knowledge and abilities of the 2013 generation, which can be used in the association process has lower percentage marks because of the components in the human capital completion into those that fall before the year. This affirms that CNU Education graduates has competed the society since they were already hired for employment. According to Brennan et. al.

Table 2: Number of Graduates Employed either teaching or non-teaching

Degree Program & Specialization	2012					2013					2014				
	No. of Graduates Employed	Teaching	%	Non-teaching	%	No. of Graduates Employed	Teaching	%	Non-teaching	%	No. of Graduates Employed	Teaching	%	Non-teaching	%
BEED Gen Ed	135	120	88.9%	15	11.1%	86	75	87.2%	11	12.8%	115	113	98.26%	2	1.74%
BEED ECE	90	79	87.8%	11	12.2%	50	45	90%	5	10%	54	51	94.4%	3	5.56%
BEED SPED	82	69	84.1%	13	15.9%	51	44	86.3%	7	13.7%	82	81	98.78%	1	1.21%
BSED Math	76	68	89.5%	8	10.5%	47	40	85.1%	7	14.9%	64	63	98.44%	1	1.56%
BSED English	82	71	86.6%	11	13.4%	52	48	92.3%	4	14.7%	85	82	96.47%	3	3.66%
BSED Filipino	22	16	72.7%	6	27.3%	10	8	80%	2	7.7%	31	31	100%	0	0
BSED Soc. Studies	11	9	81.8%	2	18.2%	4	4	100%	0	20%	17	17	100%	0	0
BSED Physical Science	16	14	87.5%	2	12.5%	8	7	87.5%	1	0%	11	10	90.9%	1	9.1%
BSED Biological Science	19	17	89.5%	2	10.5%	11	10	90.9%	1	12.5%	22	20	90.9%	2	9.1%
BSED MAPEH	15	13	86.7%	2	13.3%	15	12	80%	3	9.1%	24	21	87.5%	3	1.25%
BSED TLE	5	5	100%	0	0	4	4	100%	0	20%	8	8	100%	0	0

(2003) as cited in Boholano (2012), the employability of English graduates is rather poor light; at six months after graduation over half of English graduates were in full-time paid employment but this was below the proportions for all English major graduates.

As shown in the table only BSED TLE AND Social Studies major graduates are all employed as teachers. Not only because they are very few but this proves that graduates in this subject area are in demand. Skills learned from this area are also needed in preparing these high school students, their future learners to be prepared in vocational and technical skills which can lead them for employment even if they could not yet finish a baccalaureate degree. The second in rank in 2014 is the English majors. This could also be related to their jobs as tutors because they are not yet legally employed as professional teachers. Many of these English majors now are tutoring foreign students like Koreans, Japanese and even Germans who are residing in the city. Some just simply continued to be tutors because they have been doing it since they were still students. This is one of their part time jobs. This is related to this idea based on an analysis conducted between June to December 2006' It was found that the most highly valued generic skills are oral and written communication skills, interpersonal skills, ability to work in a team, problem solving and decision making skills, leadership and computer literacy (Ranjit Singh Malhi 2008). Written and oral communication skills and critical thinking are just some of the strengths mentioned by English graduates themselves which will qualify them to be employed in private sectors (Boholano, 2012).

Furthermore, the analysis found that the key traits employers are keen to look for are on the achievement orientation such as self-motivation, proactive, high integrity, reliable, able to work independently with minimal supervision, emotionally stable and able to perform well under pressure.

The BSED Biological Sciences is the third in the rank because many teachers in the elementary are needed both in private and public schools. Most of these young graduates now are teaching in private schools because they are accepted even if they are not yet board Passers. However, majority of these graduates were really employed as teachers. Only in 2013, where BSED Social Studies and Filipino graduates more were employed not in teaching but were in the call centers. This is the employment where what they have learned from the university like communication skills can easily be applied. Some of our MAPEH majors are occupied in being choreographers and party organizers so they did not yet seek employment in teaching.

The main reason why not all are teaching is that teaching plantilla is not commensurate to the number of graduates. Comparing school years 2012-2013, it is very evident that in the previous year many are already working and mostly are hired as teachers already. This is the effect of having one year already after graduation. Some of them had rested after being students, after a year they already decided to start working. Many said they are already ashamed from their parents to always ask money so they started to. The clear cut issue in this case is that many of the local institutions of higher learning; both public and private like Cebu Normal University have not failed to offer a sufficiently rigorous education to produce the necessary quality in the workforce which the industry requires." Wetch (1970) as cited in Boholano (2012) argues that education and skill possession produce two effects-----more pay and more productivity. In the same study, it is found out that basic skill, attitude and behaviors were very important to be employed, while competence was seriously considered in the supplementary education industry

Table 3: Reasons Provided by the Teachers for Wanting to Change Current Job

The Table presents certain reasons why teachers want to change their teaching career. As gleaned from the data, twenty percent (20%) of the teacher –respondents admit that oftentimes teacher salaries are not released on time hence they are prompted to borrow a certain amount of money from the loan sharks with a sizeable amount of interest rate. Married ones expressed that sometimes they experience sending promissory notes to the schools of their children for the permission to take either Mid- term or Final examinations. Likewise, for the single ones, aside from giving financial support to their parents, they too, help in their siblings’ even their immediate relatives’ education. Further during the interview, majority noted that had the salary be given on time they could have stayed put as teachers because teaching is what they have been trained for but for practical reasons, they leave and land another job with the assurance that they go back to teaching once they become financially stable.

Another reason why these teachers want to change their current job as teachers is their limited opportunity for promotion with nineteen percent (19%) data on record. Conscious of the scenario that teacher promotion especially in the Department of Education is somewhat hierarchical, thus longer time is still needed to climb up the ladder. A few even noted although based only on observation, that ranking of teachers is done subjectively. On the positive note however, some admit that before they get promoted they need to enroll themselves in further studies. This somehow made them feel that “going up” takes a longer time considering that almost always teachers retire first from the teaching job at the age of 65 before position becomes vacant. Thereafter competition becomes stiff.

Seventeen percent (17%) of the respondents also shared that another reason why they left the teaching career is the security of tenure. They believe that while they are in the teaching service they feel uncertain of their future. According to them, since they are still young, chances are qualifications become stringent thus priority is given to those teachers who have advanced experience in teaching.

Having low motivation with fifteen percent (15%) respondents agreeing, stated that they lack the inspiration and encouragement to go further teaching hence they transferred to another career. They further noted that primarily, teaching is their parents’ choice. Secondly as observed, oftentimes newcomers to the teaching job are assigned to teach in far-flung areas where they feel

“away from civilization.” They added that with their desire to teach in central schools, they just couldn’t because of the so-called hierarchical process. Apart from these, they see that most of our schools now are wanting in instructional materials, added to 60-70 students in a class and not to mention varied behaviors of students coming from the different family backgrounds. These scenarios obviously stunt their motivation to teach.

Down the line is fourteen percent (14%) of the respondents articulated that since professional training is seldom offered to them, they are carried away to go out of teaching and look for another job. As observed, the same teachers are oftentimes given the chance to attend relevant trainings and seminars. Somehow they are disoriented since in the undergraduate studies, they learn that to further develop their teaching competence teachers especially the new ones are the first priority to such. What happens is if there are seminars open for teachers, they personally attend but pay for the registration themselves. Aside from that, they are absent from their classes. Things like these made them realize that professional upliftment entails a long process as well.

One reason which the respondents rated the lowest percentage of thirteen percent (13%) in terms of reasons of transferring is that environment is not friendly. Obviously classes both in elementary and secondary are generally crowded most especially in the public schools. Coupled to that is the large number of students per class. Thus they declared that since this issue is immemorial it is remote that things would improve that soon. Being in this situation hampers their enthusiasm because understandably improvement in this aspect is based on the national decision among policy makers.

5 CONCLUSION

The study presented the percentage of employment of the teacher education graduates of Cebu Normal University. Based on the findings of the study, the graduates are employable in different schools either public or private. The teacher education graduates and qualified to teach based in their own field of specialization. Graduates from a normal school who is Center of Excellence in Education is better the other graduates. Thus, it is very evident that the graduates in Cebu Normal University are employable in school and other agencies.

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